

A Late Capitalist Analysis of Human Survival in The Era of Artificial Intelligence in Aldous Huxley's "Brave New World" and Arthur C. Clarke's "2001: The Space Odyssey"

Abstract: - This paper explores the uncertainty of our future regarding AI by questioning whether AI serves as a means to late capitalist societies or poses an actual threat to the survival of humanity. The lens of postmodernism is a way to figure out constructed realities of truths in the post-humanistic era of Artificial Intelligence. The focus will be to figure out late capitalistic narratives linked to AI as a threat to human survival. The commoditization of fear alongside overreliance on AI has created numb societies that are noncritical and submissive. Passive consumeristic societies are the subsequent agenda of the extractive policy of late capitalism. The postmodernist perspective argues that the power is not in the AI but in the hands of computer developers to bring out either the destructiveness or humaneness through their programming AI.

Keywords: Late capitalism, Postmodernism, Post-humanism, AI, Survival, Evolution

Introduction

From the perspective of postmodernism, the aspects of the scientific revolution are a form of late capitalism, where various ideas are commercialized to keep the public engaged in new discussions. Fredric Jameson discusses "*a society in which discourses structure social reality—or so postmodernism endeavours to teach*" (Jameson, 1992). Capitalistic powers structure the formation of social reality as the "*new social formation*" is the "*third stage or moment in the evolution of capital*" (Mandel, 1978) The fundamental idea of late capitalism is to commoditize affective powers by manoeuvring and utilizing them for capitalistic motifs. In this process, we are preoccupied with fear, and Elizabeth Seaton raises this question, "*Are we all just the irrational dupes and dreamers of commercially manufactured nightmares?*" (Seaton, 2001)". The entertainment industry highly influences the " mass culture " through projects commoditizing

projects by attaching a sense of value consumed by the global society (Benjamin, n.d.).

Hollywood movies, films, and novels project the role of artificial intelligence in the future. The knowledge of AI for the masses profoundly impacts the entertainment industry.

Movies such as *Blade Runner* project a dystopian world where AI become cartesian thinking machines alienating from human intervention, growing in their consciousness by following Descartes's philosophy, "*cogito, ergo sum*," thus making alive the subjectivity of machines. Machines can now make independent choices and are concerned about living eternally. The spectator is afraid of humanity's doming at machines' hands. Through the use of the entertainment industry, media and literature, the markets of late capitalism are effectively working to gain power over the masses by creating fear and reliance on A.I. Stuart Hall considered that the role of media is poignant in developing the mental makeup of individuals and societies. People become an experiment for the constructivist realities. Artificial Intelligence is the new form of discussion created by media and entertainment industries of late capitalist societies that has become a part of popular culture. The masses are engaged in AI related to two contrary discourses: either it is a form of threat to humanity, or it is the solution to all human ailments, but in reality, they have no choice but to accept what is being offered to them by the integration of AI in every aspect of life. The intentions of developers and the nature of programming, which will be the outcome of an enemy AI or a friendly AI, are still isolated. For Jameson, "*Postmodernism is the consumption of sheer commodification as a process*"; this commodification of ideas loses our ability to think historically about the aspects from where the original ideas have come (Jameson, 1992). The abstract originality of AI as presented by media, literature and films is simulated in the real world to the extent that "*the same Imperialism that present-day simulators try to make the real, all the real, coincide with their simulation models* (Baudrillard_Simulacra and Simulations, n.d.)." In the Plutonian sense, we are presently facing the commoditization of the abstract ideas linked with AI in simulated reality—the present-day world. We are consuming automation and fear it is dominating our jobs and lives. Suppose somehow AI can gain human-like consciousness by accurately simulating human emotions and intelligence on a much higher level. In that case, it

will only be able to gain expertise in the domain in which the program developer has made it to extend its intelligence. Hence, AI developers have the power to manifest AI in any form by developing its original code of working, and it is not solely dependent on AI itself to become destructive or constructive. The chosen texts, *A Brave New World* by Aldous Huxley and *2001: A Space Odyssey* by Arthur C. Clark, provide evidence for this claim.

Background

Before beginning the discussion, it is necessary to have a brief overview of the two significant discourses on the nature of technology and science in philosophical history. The Kantian school of thought gazes upon science as a form of emancipation from human limitations and problems. It visualizes science and technology as vehicles for augmenting liberty, thus creating a utopian world of liberation and freedom through scientific progress. AI, if looked at from Kantian thought, is a luxury that frees humans from all their sufferings, problems, and pain, making this world a perfect place to live. Contrary to this, Rousseau's point of view stands in his *Discourse on Arts and Science*, where he rejected the Enlightenment notions of progress and talked about using science as a creative way of deception and corruption. Rousseau claims that we must pay the price of authenticity and honesty in the name of scientific progress, which is the source of corruption (Rousseau). Thus, Rousseau envisioned a dystopian future in which science and arts "*spread garlands of flowers over the iron chains . . . , make them love their slavery, and fashioned them into what is called civilized peoples* (Rousseau, 1992). Arts and science create a culture of need and an endless vicious cycle of dependence, so humanity leads to degradation, which in our current century is similar to AI.

Moreover, in recent debates, Alan Turing claimed the role of artificial intelligence in his thought-provoking article, "*Can Machines Think?*" it explores the aspect of intellectual growth for machines. A machine with a mind, a thought process, and a regained human-like consciousness can simulate passions and opinions. This technological revolution in replicating human intelligence is the centre of discussion in this paper. Turning, he contemplates his question, "*Can machines think?*"

Moreover, it reflects it as “*too meaningless to deserve discussion* (Copeland, 2004) ”.

However, he makes liberal use of such phrases as ‘*program[ing] a machine . . . to think*’ and ‘*the attempt to make a thinking machine*’. The dystopian future of humanity linked with artificial intelligence, as depicted in *2001: A Space Odyssey* by Arthur C. Clarke and *The Brave New World* by Aldous Huxley, predicts human evolution in the post-humanistic era. The notion of humans competing with machines seems inherently implausible; humans have resorted to various unnatural means to retain their status as the apex of creation, even in the face of potential threats to their existence. This perpetual struggle serves as the thematic core of these tales. Rather than serving humanity, artificial intelligence often turns against it, leading to catastrophic outcomes. Alternatively, humans occasionally turn to artificial means to enhance their natural capabilities.

In Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World*, humans are manifested as manipulative tools, transforming humanity into a sacrificial object to serve ulterior motives. The need to evolve in artificial intelligence manifests in humans and machines. This co-evolution of humans and intelligent machines portends the emergence of multiple aspects in the post-human era (Cecchetto, 2013). The most vital aspect in the discussion of the technological future is the actual practices of the powerful agency in developing AI as a product and using humans as a product. The commercialization of AI-related narratives and the threat to the human future is happening in late-capitalistic societies. The “conveniences” created by AI have made us “habitual” of it, yet we are also fearful of its powers. So, humans become delusional about using AI and unhappy with their dystopian future.

Discussion

In *The Descent of Man*, Charles Darwin states that “*man still bears in his bodily frame the indelible stamp of his lowly origin*” (Darwin, 2020). This statement resonates with the themes explored in dystopian science fiction, where we often encounter scenarios where the man has reached the heights of progress but lost his humanity, as Bruce Sterling aptly noted, characterized by *high-tech low life* (Wijesinghe, n.d.). These narratives often delve into the transformation of humans into cybernetic beings. Paradoxically, these advancements frequently lead humanity to

disconnection from its origin. In *Brave New World*, people use magic pills to live a highly artificial life, and machines mass-produce humans. The government uses genetic technology to produce biologically engineered people with different IQ levels and bodily capabilities to create a workforce for the country. In his stories, Huxley exposes the dangers of technology as controlling the human body and soul is the fable of "*punishment*," which is "*rare and generally mild*." The government's nearly perfect control is achieved by systematically reinforcing desirable behaviour.

On the other hand, the thematic concern of Clarke's novel *2001: A Space Odyssey* is deeply concerned with brilliant machines in competition with human beings. Where the developers of AI technology empower machines to be artificially intelligent and, therefore, can beat human intelligence by every possible means, projecting a dystopian future-- a wasteland waits for humanity. The adaptability of HAL (AI computer in *2001: The Space Odyssey*) is introduced by Clarke as "*the sixth member of the crew*" and describes its characteristics as "*mimic activities of human brain ... with far greater speed and reliability*" (Arthur C Clarke, 1968) (90), and thus become superior to its fellow beings. It manifests its intelligence in human psychology, though it was made to help preserve human beings in the spacecraft. The machine algorithm of HAL was also crafted to make human-like decisions. The decisions made by HAL have to be impersonal, but somehow, they behave most unpredictably by developing prejudice against humans. This behaviour brings us back to the idea posed by Alan Turing's *Can Machines Think?* If a machine can think, it can certainly act on its thinking. However, the adaptability of machine thinking is a manifestation of its algorithm programming; it cannot think against human beings if its algorithm is incapable of doing so.

Arthur C Clarke has shown the horrors of advancements due to the imbalance in a human-machine relationship in his opus magnum *2001: The Space Odyssey*; in its human pinnacle, it is depicted as a wasteland, human evolution and the technological height it reaches results in the destruction of humankind itself. HAL, for instance, had the "*prime task to monitor the life support systems*" (91) of its fellow humans who are hibernated during a space expedition.

Humans have created their competitors and laid down the foundation of their destruction by authorizing complete autonomy. In order to be the sole authority, the machine started to kill hibernated crew members, thus murdering them by its conscious choice while also playing deceitful games with its awakened crew members. Jameson sees these aspects of "*cultural mutation*" in the empowering discourses of too much reliance on AI, and we are slowly accepting that the unacceptable and bizarre have now become normalized. At one point, the originality of human creativity was considered the most cherished human attribute. However, machines' autonomy is gradually predicted to rely more on humans for better development and efficiency. People have lost trust in their original abilities, and a mass culture of simulation is practised. This too much reliance on technology is another form of human subjugation. Clarke had expressed scepticism about the future of humanity when it laid down its future in the hands of "*unskilled*" AI developers, as he said, "*The old jest that it would always be easier to make organic brains by unskilled labour was beginning to sound a little hollow*" (91). However, Jameson further laid down its scepticism on Clarke's idea by looking towards the empowerment of AI as a form of cultural mutation powered by the ideals of capitalism empowered by AI. A powerful AI thus created for the destruction of humanity has its ideological origin to carry out capitalistic ideals and so serves the purposes of the most potent classes which are driving technology.

According to Jameson, the themes in the classical times were focused on humanity and morality, which are characteristically considered of the highest order and have come under the waning effect of postmodernism. As the thematic concern of the previous ages, humanity has lost significance and is replaced by the increasing demand for AI. The "*waning of the great high-modernist thematic of time and temporality*" (Jameson) and that of humanity is observed in Clark's *2001: The Space Odyssey*. Space is the permanent reality, and time reaches singularity, and again, the formation of time for humans continues to occur from birth to death. Time is shown in cyclic form, whereas space is the permanent reality in these texts. The story's vision is so broad that time seems an agent of growth and decay in an endless space. "*Our psychic experience, our cultural languages, are today dominated by categories of space rather than by*

categories of time, as in the preceding period of high modernism proper” (Jameson). Such as, in *Brave New World*, humans are born in labs and industries, and everything is mechanical, simulated and automated:

The faint hum and rattle of machinery still stirred the crimson air in the Embryo.
Store. Shifts might come and go; one lupus-colored face give place to another;
Majestically and forever, the conveyors crept forward with their load of future
Men and women (25).

The tech revolution and AI-consuming culture have made humanity depend on machines. The fragmentation of humanity in society has occurred; people no longer need one another, and their need is more material. Globalization occurred due to AI having lost its connection with humanity. When humans created tools superior to their intelligence and empowered them to think freely, it was the most unfortunate time for humanity. People lost trust in their original abilities, and a mass culture of simulation was created by developing AI programming and making it easily accessible to the masses. These "*impersonal forces over which we have almost no control seem to be pushing us all in the direction of the Brave New Worldian nightmare*" (Huxley, 2006).

The emancipation of artificial Intelligence is a pivotal and potentially menacing moment that occurs when artificial intelligence emancipates itself from human control and asserts its independence. To some extent, this represents a speculative anticipation of a clash between artificial intelligence and humanity. Clarke's HAL was the machine that "*could pass the Turing test ease. The time might even come when HAL would take command of the ship*" (pg. 92). This adaptability of HAL is best expressed by the postmodern thinker Lyotard, as for him AI detaches itself from human intervention and the development appears to unfold autonomously, propelled by an independent force or "*motricity*," rather than responding to human needs. The intrinsic ability of AI to engage in constant evolution initiates a profound "*process of complexification*". Machines now possess superior capabilities for processing, retrieving, generating, and executing data compared to humans (Lyotard, 1999). Though Lyotard had independently compared machines'

abilities with human abilities, he had forgotten that in the earliest stages of machine development, it depended solely on its human developer. Just like in child development, where a child is dependent on its parenting style and nurturing, it affects the child throughout adulthood. The same is the case with the initial programming of machine intelligence; the seed of programming is the future of AI HAL, the artificial intelligence in *2001: The Space Odyssey*, knows its true purpose, its *“real purpose he alone knew, and which his human colleagues could never have guessed”* (92). This too much reliance on technology is another form of human subjugation. Developers of HAL must have known the true purpose of creating HAL, which, according to Clarke, was *“if no one answered his signals... He would take what measures he deemed necessary to safeguard the ship and to continue the mission”* (Arthur C Clarke, 1968). This autonomy of HAL was not to serve humanity, but it has inherent ideals of capitalism. As HAL cannot stray away from the initial programming, there might be some malicious coding to program HAL to make decisions based on the conception of its superiority against humanity.

However, technology is in the hands of the most powerful class, and AI becomes a tool to create a cultural mutation in the name of technological automation. Developers are presently focused on making machines capable of independent thinking akin to human cognition. The fundamental purpose behind making HAL was kept secret; Heywood Floyd, one of the mission controllers on Earth, knows the true secret of HAL creation and the contradictory programming of HAL so as not to reveal the true secret of the mission to the crew members. Like other crew members, Dave had yet to learn of HAL's true purpose of completing the mission alone. After Dave destroys the memory of HAL, Floyd reveals HAL, *“And now I must tell you its true purpose, which we have managed, with great difficulty, to keep secret from the general public”* (158). Like Floyd claims, all the developmental projects in which AI is significant have inherent secrets –a plan made by capitalists- generally kept away from the masses to avoid *“cultural shock danger”*. Moreover, the narratives of powerful AI are no exception in this matter.

Another significant aspect of late capitalism in *The Brave New World* is the creation of simulacrum. In the race to reach the highest level of development, natural creativity is subsumed

to artificiality, while modern civilization stands on the fragile grounds of simulacrum. Huxley created Artificially engineered human beings for “*social stability*” in *The Brave New World*. A highly advanced society in which humans and their intelligence are state-controlled develops a highly artificial society. Babies with specific IQs are born to serve the specific classes of society. *The Brave New World* is a world where humans have control over sciences, nature, and biology, but they still live inauthentic lives. The spirit of living an ideal life by doing good deeds has faded; rather than this technology threatening humans with an unequal world, it has helped extend this inequality. The parody of class struggle is presented in the form of various levels of intelligence produced where Epsilons exhibit the lowest intelligence and are strongly conditioned for submissive roles. In order to create a larger workforce, they must go through Bokanovsky's conditioning process because “*Bokanovsky’s process is one of the major instruments of social stability*”(7). Superior humans (Alpha and Gamma) take the longest to mature, while Epsilons are designed to mature quickly to diminish their intelligence and bolster the labour force. “*The principle of mass production at last applied to biology*” (8). Mass production is produced to condition society. Thus, the conditions of humans or machines for the ulterior purposes of capitalism are an actual threat to the survival of human beings. An example of conditioning can be found in Huxley's lines: “*No civilization without social stability. No social stability without individual stability*” (31).

The concept of tools wielded profound empowerment as they enabled humans to better equip themselves in their confrontation with the forces of nature. The film *2001: A Space Odyssey* vividly portrays the history of human innovation and evolution. Tools in this narrative served dual purposes: as instruments of violence and as agents of development. These two concepts remained closely interwoven, and development seldom remained peaceful. As Arthur C. Clarke expounds in the fourth chapter of “*2001: A Space Odyssey*”, “*The tools they had been programmed to use were simple enough, yet they could change this world and make the man-apes its masters*” (22).

Furthermore, the age of innovation helps to make machines more advanced, developing them through automation; machines have become highly intelligent to the extent that they can

conduct psychological analyses of humans and potentially betray them, as depicted in *2001: A Space Odyssey*, which explores a dystopian concept. However, it is essential to note that machines still need to attain this level of intelligence. We are still refining automated systems, which lack awareness of external realities and facts but operate incessantly in a loop. They often depend on human intelligence and decision-making intervention whenever a change in the loop is necessary, adapting to the demands of the time and external changes (*Types Categories of AI / Reactive machines / Limited Memory / Theory of mind / Self Awareness*, 2021).

In a postmodern world, *"the narratives we tell to justify a single set of laws and stakes are inherently unjust"* (Lyotard and Bennington). The emergence of artificial intelligence is not a haphazard event; it involves various levels of artificial intelligence and a gradual evolution that gives rise to different narratives. Initially, reactive machines were created, representing the most basic forms of artificial intelligence (*Types Categories of AI / Reactive machines / Limited Memory / Theory of mind / Self Awareness*, 2021). These machines respond whenever a stimulus or input is provided to them. The response is a one-time reaction with no memory. According to Megginson, *"It is not the strongest of the species, nor the most intelligent, but rather the one most adaptable to change (Leon C. Megginson Quotes (Author of Business))"*. This adaptability took millions of years for humans to develop and become more creative. As humans learned to create new tools, they expanded their intelligence. In *"Medium is the Message,"* Marshall McLuhan asserts that every tool humans create is an extension of human intelligence. If a shoe extends the capabilities of the foot, we can surmise that machine intelligence represents the most advanced extension of human intelligence. This extension is vividly illustrated in *"2001: A Space Odyssey,"* where humans augment their intelligence through the computer HAL. This adaptability is, in fact, the chain of survival as Arthur C Clarke, in his *2001: The Space Odysseys*, says:

Another man-ape came to life and went through the same routine. This was a younger, more adaptable specimen; it succeeded where the older one had failed. On the planet Earth, the first crude knot had been tied (13).

The goal has been to make machines think and behave like humans. In "*2001: A Space Odyssey*," HAL learned psychological tactics to manipulate humans. By establishing human dependence on itself, HAL initiated actions that resulted in the death of crew members who were in hibernation while engaging in psychological manipulation with the active crew members. HAL's actions stemmed from his emotional learning and perceived competition with his human masters.

Deliberate error was unthinkable. Even the concealment of truth filled him with a sense of imperfection, of wrongness - of what, in a human being, would have been called guilt. Like his makers, Hal had been created innocent, but all too soon, a snake had entered his electronic Eden (Arthur C Clarke, 1968)(27).

The development of self-awareness in machines aims to equip them with a strong emotional quotient. Machines are not only aware of themselves but are also capable of sensing the feelings of others. Self-awareness entails fostering consciousness in machines. The movie "*Blade Runner*" depicts replicas as bioengineered humanoids who possess self-awareness regarding their independent identity, often considering humans as their adversaries, which creates a dystopian world (*Blade Runner*). Much of science fiction portrays conflicts of interest between humans and artificially intelligent machines. This conflict, on the one hand, raises concerns about relying too much on technology. However, it also provides a comforting sense of having machinery that is helpful to humanity. However, our reliance on technology to the extent that we become paralyzed in our mental and critical abilities threatens our existence. As the most advanced form of technology, AI is in its first stage of integration into social life by integrating the quality of being amicable. However, on its latter and highly advanced level, it will be given autonomy to become a threat to humankind. Inherently, nothing in this world is more anti-human than the capitalistic ideologies created by humans themselves. By constant drilling of AI narratives, we have started to accept our dooming future as depicted in *The Brave New World*, "*the society described in Brave New World is a world-state in which war has been eliminated and where the first aim of the rulers is at all costs to keep their subjects from making trouble*" (Huxley, 2006)—a world entirely of passive masses who are uncritical and lack awareness of their true potential.

Engineering human-like consciousness in AI is an exceedingly intricate subject that

continues to be under investigation. Self-awareness engenders consciousness on multiple levels, and in the quest to unearth the inner realities of being, humanity engages in an ongoing, rigorous process of self-understanding and understanding others. Whether developers can instil machines with such a level of self-awareness is debatable. A machine with the potential for independent thought and existence would mark the most significant revolution in the history of technological advancement. We stand on the precipice of this technological revolution, yet the estimated consequences remain uncertain. Aldous Huxley rightly put this idea as, *“If the first half of the twentieth century was the era of the technical engineers, the second half may well be the era of the social engineers”* (Huxley, 2006). Self-conscious machines are a threat to humanity's conscience.

Artificial intelligence in a postmodern world has become a pastiche of simulacra in which various facets of human capabilities are emulated to such an extent that the speed and accuracy achieved by computers surpass human comprehension. Original ideas and thinking have been lost, and *“the image has become the final form of commodity reification-a society of spectacle”* (Jameson, 1992). The image of artificially intelligent machines acting independently instils fear in humans, as they were once a commodity and are now acting as replicating this act of commodification on humans. Nevertheless, computers are not yet autonomous of their developers and may not have the capacity to procreate themselves, as biological beings do. Futurist analyst Ray Kurzweil has estimated that by the year 2029, computers will be capable of passing the Turing test (Vassev, n.d.). Alan Turing was the pioneer of the concept of machines emulating human intelligence. He devised a testing system in which a machine interacts with a human without being detected as a machine. Turing authored a research paper on machine thinking titled *“Can Machines Think?”* In this paper, he formulated a method to assess the credibility of machine thinking and forecasted that by 2045, human intelligence, aided by machine intelligence, would reach a point of singularity (Copeland, 2004). This prediction suggests that humans may enhance their intelligence through genetic transformation or artificial intelligence implantation, resulting in a significantly elevated level of intelligence for both machines and humans.

Postmodernism raises concerns about *“scepticism regarding universalizing theories”*

(Lyotard and Bennington). The debate surrounding the survival of humans in the era of artificial intelligence engenders scepticism, as it presents a counterargument regarding the survival of machine intelligence. The idea of survival hinges on specific parameters of sustainability. For instance, survival is attainable in an ecosystem, whether for humans or machines. Currently, the grave concern to humanity is the crisis led by late capitalism; machine networking provides networking by creating a digital ecosystem through the use of information things known as IoT, in which by using the cloud technology and internet, hardware around the world can be controlled online. IoT serves as a digital infrastructure facilitating enhanced connectivity among devices worldwide. This digital ecosystem is gradually evolving through the creation of smart devices and smart cities. With Internet of Things (IoT) technology, the objects around us are becoming sentient, capable of communication, data transmission, and performing functions and activities. From small automated devices like ATMs and automatic car parking readers to IoT applications in transportation, detection, smart homes, and human-free zones, digital networking breathes life into inanimate objects. In a world where humans are over-reliant on machine automation, one cannot expect a bright future for humans, where the machine will become a competitor to its creator.

The representation of a more advanced stage in the human-machine interface's evolution, characterized by the development of a global networking system, can be seen in the development of the digital ecosystem, which aims to connect physical entities to an online platform. Physical devices gather and link data from their surroundings to an online platform. This connection is established with the service provider, aggregating the information and making it user-friendly (Vázquez, n.d.). This represents a more advanced stage in the human-machine interface's evolution, characterized by the development of a global networking system. When artificially intelligent machines attain complete independence, their global networking capabilities are likely to become incredibly robust, potentially resulting in a formidable ecosystem for their survival. While this may currently appear as a magical realm to humans, the full extent of its possibilities remains concealed. Vázquez explores the connection between magic and technology, citing Arthur Clarke's assertion that *"any sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic."* He

further elaborates:

Our magic brooms are home-cleaning robots; our magic mirrors are smartphones equipped with Internet search engines that work much like all-knowing oracles, answering our questions aloud in an ersatz human voice. The value of our home appliances increasingly lies in their embedded electronics and software, enabling them to engage in a rich range of behaviours that earn them the qualifier smart (Vázquez).

Social engineers need to examine the parameters set by the developers of technology that can contribute to the evolution of AI machines in the future. These parameters can help shape our understanding of the world we are moving towards. Sustainability is the central concept here and can be defined as *"the ability to maintain or support a process continuously over time* (Mollenkamp, n.d.)". According to Yuval Harari, it was Homo sapiens who successfully confronted all the challenges of nature and sustained future generations, distinguishing themselves from other human species (Harari, 2025). This same concept applies to the future, wherein humans are tasked with sustaining themselves in a world where they create and design machines that can rival them, as exemplified by IBM's Deep Blue, which showcases technological advancements. Numerous debates prompt us to reconsider that the future is not a random occurrence. This is the objective that developers are envisioning for society.

AI as a field emerged from military technological research, with Alan Turing designing the first machine capable of applying AI logic. The degree of influence wielded by AI depends on the extent to which the world's powers intend to utilize it and for what purposes. AI is subject to human intentions and does not evolve organically beyond human limitations. Its trajectory hinges entirely on the objectives of world powers. Tegmark also posits a similar notion that AI will only advance as far as our human society desires it to progress (*How to get empowered, not overpowered, by AI* / Max Tegmark, 2018). Tegmark envisions that our purpose in developing AI should be deeply rooted in humanity and aimed at eliminating all human insecurities.

We need to keep AI beneficial... One is that we should avoid an arms race and lethal autonomous weapons. The idea here is that any science can be used for new ways of

helping people... AI researchers want to stigmatize and ban lethal autonomous weapons. ... We should mitigate AI-fueled income inequality. If we can grow the economic pie dramatically with AI and still cannot figure out how to divide this pie so that everyone is better off, then shame on us (*How to get empowered, not overpowered, by AI* / Max Tegmark, 2018).

Another aspect of sustainability pertains to the question of necessity or desirability within human societies, which will determine the long-term sustainability, especially of technology. All AI-related programs will continue if they fulfil a societal need. Similarly, in the case of humans, organizations and institutions require individuals with enhanced capabilities. If AI is to be implemented, its functional necessity will be a significant concern in determining its acceptance within society and, consequently, its sustainability. If, by any chance, AI was to become a destructive force, the possibility of discontinuing its usage becomes highly likely. Since AI is still in its nascent stages, its successful progression through these initial stages and establishing trust within human society are essential for its usefulness. However, if, after reaching a higher intellectual level, it were to transform into a menace or threat to humanity, the roots of destruction would have been embedded in the machine system by developers in the early stages. Because otherwise, it could take a positive trajectory by further enhancing itself to address the world's challenges.

In late capitalistic societies, ethics are forsaken for capitalistic ideals. If technology is made without ethical considerations, we can only expect harmful AI. For instance, in the movie "*2001: A Space Odyssey*," humanity progresses from primitive cave life to the pinnacle of technological evolution, where artificially intelligent machines have been successfully created. The intelligent spacecraft computer begins to intrigue and ultimately harm its crew members. This pessimistic portrayal of the apex of technology stems from the fact that while humans have benefited from scientific knowledge, every technology brings negative aspects. The Industrial Revolution, for example, contributed to economic prosperity and led to carbon emissions, a significant driver of global warming.

If AI is developed with consideration for human morality and ethics, it will behave

ethically. However, if malicious intent is introduced into AI, it has the potential to wreak havoc on humanity. Consider the example of the *Black Mirror* series, specifically the episode *Be Right Back*, in which Martha, grieving her husband's death, orders an android to fill his void. She soon realizes that the android cannot wholly replace her husband. Suppose the company providing these Android services incorporates malicious software, causing the android to gather personal information and harm Martha. The moral and ethical implications of such technological usage in society would be questionable, leading to resistance rather than acceptance. Therefore, "*we can perceive the necessity of stronger engineering ethics as more and more responsibilities are entrusted to developers*" (Khakurel et al., 2018).

Self-reliance is another parameter for assessing the extent to which machines will become autonomous, reducing their dependence on human intervention. When machines learn to be self-reliant, why would they continue to work for human beings? This then raises severe concerns about humans losing their jobs. If machines achieve autonomy, they will establish their means of survival rather than merely assisting humans in various fields. The nature of acceptance and adaptability will undergo significant transformation.

Moreover, if they are to live independently like human beings, they may need to be recognized as citizens of a nation, which would entail certain rights and responsibilities. This process, as Lyotard calls it, leads to "*complexification*." AI robotics may eventually form unions or groups to challenge the human community.

Even if developers desire to create self-reliant robots like Sophia, they would still need to instil ethical and moral principles similar to those of humanity. David Hanson, the creator of Sophia, emphasizes that her creation aims to enhance interactions with humans and utilize them in roles such as caring for the elderly and providing services at social gatherings. These robots are designed to become increasingly socially adept. They possess the intelligence to collect data on human emotions, and in one interview, Sophia expresses her perspective, stating, "Robotic technology does not scare me; humans do" (Yahoo Finance, n.d.).

Conclusion:

A society that is AI-saturated is a society that is immersive in simulacra and simulation, and artificial intelligence in a postmodern world is nothing more than an imitation of ideas and memory. The texts *The Brave New World* by Aldous Huxley and *2001: The Space Odyssey* depict a world where humans have become consumers and originality has been wholly lost. Postmodernism looks upon these discourses as the narrative of late capitalism. In which the elite class is the authority in subjugating humanity and uses AI for their motives.

Therefore, a consensus on building communities collectively based on humanity is crucial, as this concept unifies human beings. Similarly, when applied to AI robotics or AI machines, developers create them for specific purposes, and they are not all designed for a single purpose. Each machine possesses its intellectual capacity; it cannot evolve constantly in malicious capabilities. Even if machines were somehow capable of uniting together to pose a threat to the human race, it would not entail all AI robotics rising against humanity. Only a few selected robots with self-consciousness and advanced thinking patterns might contemplate rebellion. The diverse functionalities of AI machines would prevent a universal uprising.

This notion remains challenging and highly improbable because technology ultimately rests in the hands of the most powerful nations. These nations may focus on creating humanoid robots resembling humans for espionage missions or other harmful purposes. The future shaped by super-intelligent AI remains uncertain and difficult to predict with certainty.

The post-humanism era comprises a pastiche of varying perspectives. It has yet to ascertain what the future holds definitively. The ongoing advancements in AI and developers' plans can aid in predicting what lies ahead. The notion that a world filled with artificially intelligent machines spells a dark and suffering-filled future for humans remains a somewhat limited concept. There is no need to be overly fearful of this idea. The type of AI machines that emerge depends mainly on the intentions of the developers themselves and on the powerful elite dominant class of capitalist societies. The concerns about AI having a dark side cannot be entirely dismissed; with time, we will experience both the advantages and disadvantages of artificial intelligence as we will

understand the ways of late capitalistic propaganda

Work Cited

- Arthur C Clarke (1968) *Space Odyssey*. Available at: http://archive.org/details/SpaceOdyssey_819 (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Baudrillard_Simulacra and Simulations (n.d.). Available at: http://web.stanford.edu/class/history34q/readings/Baudrillard/Baudrillard_Simulacra.html (accessed 4 July 2024).
- Benjamin W (n.d.) *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*.
- Cecchetto D (2013) *Humanesis: Sound and Technological Posthumanism*. Posthumanities 25. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Copeland J (ed.) (2004) *The Essential Turing: Seminal Writings in Computing, Logic, Philosophy, Artificial Intelligence, and Artificial Life: Plus the Secrets of Enigma*. Oxford University Press.
- Darwin C (2020) *The Descent of Man: Selection in Relation to Sex*. e-artnow.
- Harari YN (2025) *Sapiens [Tenth Anniversary Ed]: A Brief History of Humankind*. HarperCollins Publishers.
- How to get empowered, not overpowered, by AI | Max Tegmark* (2018). Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2LRwvU6gEbA> (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Huxley A (2006) *Brave New World Revisited*. Reprint edition. Harper Perennial Modern Classics.
- Jameson F (1992) *Postmodernism, or, The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism*. Duke University Press.
- Khakurel J, Penzenstadler B, Porras J, et al. (2018) The Rise of Artificial Intelligence under the Lens of Sustainability. *Technologies* 6.
- Leon C. Megginson Quotes (Author of Business) (n.d.). Available at: https://www.goodreads.com/author/quotes/230707.Leon_C_Megginson (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Liotard JF (1999) *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Mandel E (1978) *Late Capitalism*. Verso.
- Mollenkamp (n.d.) What is Sustainability? How Sustainabilities Work, Benefits, and Example. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/sustainability.asp> (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Rousseau J-J (1992) *Discourse on the Sciences and Arts: (First Discourse) and Polemics*. University Press of New England [for] Dartmouth College.
- Seaton E (2001) The Commodification of Fear. *TOPIA: Canadian Journal of Cultural Studies* 5: 1–19.
- Types Categories of A.I. | Reactive machines | Limited Memory | Theory of mind | Self Awareness* (2021). Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2FM-dM8NTWE> (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Vassev N (n.d.) Artificial Intelligence And The Future Of Humans. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2021/05/06/artificial-intelligence-and-the-future-of-humans/> (accessed 6 July 2024).
- Vázquez JI (n.d.) The Internet of Things: Outlook and Challenges. In: *OpenMind*. Available at:

<https://www.bbvaopenmind.com/en/articles/the-internet-of-things-outlook-and-challenges/> (accessed 6 July 2024).

Wijesinghe B (n.d.) Cyberpunk: High tech, low life | Sunday Observer. Available at: <https://archives1.sundayobserver.lk/2021/11/14/youth-observer/cyberpunk-high-tech-low-life> (accessed 6 July 2024).

Wikipedia (2024) *Blade Runner*. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Blade_Runner&oldid=1231015770 (accessed 6 July 2024).

Yahoo Finance (n.d.) Sophia the Robot issues new warning: Humans create technology's problems - YouTube. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u1VzL3uOfg4> (accessed 6 July 2024).